

IHTP WGS NEB Ultrall library process

Samples quantified with Biotium Accuclear Ultra high sensitivity dsDNA Quantitative kit using Mosquito LV liquid platform, Bravo WS and BMG FLUOstar Omega plate reader and cherrypicked to 200ng / 120ul using Tecan liquid handling platform.

Cherrypicked plates sheared to 450bp using a Covaris LE220 instrument.

Post sheared samples purified using Agencourt AMPure XP SPRI beads on Agilent Bravo WS.

Library construction (ER, A-tailing and ligation) using 'NEB Ultra II custom kit' on an Agilent Bravo WS automation system.

PCR set-up using KapaHiFi Hot start mix and IDT UDI 96 PCR (sets A-D) barcodes on Agilent Bravo WS automation system.

PCR cycles, 6 standard cycles (WGSUDI_6)

- 1 Incubate 95C 5 mins
- 2 Incubate 98C 30 secs
- 3 Incubate 65C 30 secs
- 4 Incubate 72C 2 mins
- 5 Cycle from 2, 5 more times
- 6 Incubate 72C 10 mins

Post PCR plate purified using Agencourt AMPure XP SPRI beads on Beckman BioMek NX96 liquid handling platform.

Libraries quantified with Biotium Accuclear Ultra high sensitivity dsDNA Quantitative kit using Mosquito LV liquid handling platform, Bravo WS and BMG FLUOstar Omega plate reader.

Libraries pooled in equimolar amounts on a Beckman BioMek NX-8 liquid handling platform.

Libraries normalised and loaded on requested Illumina sequencing platform.